

D2.2 New Mobility Cultures and Policies Hub- online platform

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INTRODUCTION

Ersilia Foundation publicly released the New Mobility Cultures and Policies Hub- online platform which will act as the first point of contact for many stakeholders and provide a portal to the project outputs and outcomes. URL address: <https://rebalancemobility.eu/>

The platform contains all information regarding project aim and progress, current status of activities, news, dissemination and instructions to take part in the project activities. Short introductions and contact details for all members of the consortium are also available.

The number of visitors, downloads, website hits will be tracked by web traffic analysis tools, allowing the consortium to overview how well the platform reaches both target groups and stakeholders.

The site will be accessible via apps on a mobile phone, on iPad or any tablet devices and on desktop devices.

In the homepage the platform invites visitors to join REBALANCE discussion by subscribing to the project newsletter where we inform subscribers about the events, released Journals and the project outcomes and outputs. The platform has links to Social media channels: LinkedIn and Twitter and.

The website is constantly updated and consequently it will be a dynamic and up-to-date source of information for target groups and stakeholders.

The website will be maintained for at least two years after the project ends.

1 SECTIONS & SUB-SECTIONS

The online platform has six main sections:

About, Activities, Talks, Journal, Insights and Observatory plus the pages allocated to the Private policy and the Contact and the links to REBALANCE social networks

About: Information about the project aims and objectives, workplan and consortium partners <https://rebalancemobility.eu/about-us/>

About

As a cultural and political initiative, the REBALANCE overall aim is to conduct an open deliberative forward looking exercise towards a transmodal transport policy strategy / theory of a paradigm shift in mobility, pushing for the most effective adoption of cultural and social values not left for consideration, better aligned with SDGs and mounting concerns about climate change. The critical review of the present plus in the light of the recent COVID pandemic which drastically affected our lifestyles, the vision over the future and the readiness to achieve it, will be embedded in Manifestos with the aim to stimulate European policymakers to adopt concrete legal and political measures while moving the wider European communities towards a radical change.

The REBALANCE Work Plan

The flowchart illustrates the REBALANCE Work Plan, starting with WP1 (Coordination & Management) leading to WP2 (Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation), WP3 (The Language of the Present), WP4 (The Needs and Hopes of the Future), and WP5 (Politics as Poetry). These work packages converge into 'The New Mobility Cultures and Policies Hub'. Below this hub, two boxes represent 'The Manifesto for a New Mobility Culture' and 'The Roadmap towards a Transport Paradigm Shift'.

The Rebalance consortium consists of 6 partners:

- INTCNA** Institute of Systems (I.S.I.S.) - Project Coordinator, Leader of WP1 & WP4
- Ernilia** Ernilia Foundation - Leader of WP2
- TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT DRESDEN** Dresden University of Technology - Leader of WP3
- Universität Göttingen** Göttingen University - Leader of WP5
- UNIVERSITY OF ZILINA** University of Zilina
- Osborne Clarke** Osborne Clarke - Legal Expertise

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the grant agreement No. 101007019

Activities: Gives a quick snapshot of the project activities
<https://rebalancemobility.eu/activities/>

Activities

REBALANCE starts from the premise that a deeper cultural reflection on how our beliefs, framed socially, influence our individual preferences is needed to better understand how we take decisions, and how policies can become positive incentives for a paradigm shift in mobility. In this regard, REBALANCE has conceived a variety of innovative consultation methods. The deliberative process will be initiated and supported by thinkers that are not necessarily directly involved in the past and current transport research debates. They will help formulating the research questions and working hypotheses, to be then addressed by a wider representation of stakeholders from the mobility and transport sector. Various workshops will set the vision for the transport system of the future and ultimately a Manifesto will be developed for a new European mobility culture and policy, to be widely diffused and promoted, and serve as a basis for further, continuing exploration beyond the REBALANCE project lifetime.

In-depth talks with thinkers

In-depth talks will be designed around the visionary thinker's work and the questions will be related to REBALANCE themes. (WP2)

[Read more](#)

Generative dialogues on theoretical framework

Dialogues with high-level mobility experts to validate the mobility cultures and values that need to shift from the economic model of the rational decision maker, looking into the fundamentals of the mobility culture of today. (WP3)

Mobility values focus groups

Focus groups to carry out a values assessment represented in current narrative involving relevant experts and stakeholders with a focus on European mobility. (WP3)

Explorative conversations on the mobility of the future

Conversations among thinkers and mobility experts in order to identify present trends, drivers, wild cards and weak signals and gain insight into possible future issues. (WP4)

Imagining future scenarios on mobility cultures

Focus Group to implement a forward-looking exercise based on an analysis of global trends and key factors that might affect the transport domain and build scenarios at 2050. (WP4)

Open consultation on the vision

Based on the scenarios space and alternative narratives identified an open consultation will be organised. (WP4)

Public interest definition focus group

To evaluate the new legal and political definition of "public interest" and its introduction into European and national regulations. (WP5)

Design a roadmap and outline feasible strategies

Back-casting exercise involving experts and stakeholders to develop a roadmap & feasible strategies to implement it. (WP5)

Co-creation of a Manifesto

Co-creative development of a Manifesto for a new European mobility culture and policy. (WP2)

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Equiparita de Camins de Catalunya @caminscat

Avui l'empresari de camins @AndreuJordi i el professor emèrit de la @UniversitatPon-Aadri Biomatèria conversen sobre l'impacte de la Covid-19 en els camins en les polítiques de mobilitat a @rebalancemobility. Segueix la conversa online bit.ly/camins088.

11 Mar 2021

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Talks: Page devoted to announce REBALANCE Talks, visitors have access to the event registration or to replay the Talk once it is published in REBALANCE youtube channel.
<https://rebalancemobility.eu/talks/>

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Journal: In this page platform visitors will find all the issues or REBALANCE quarterly publication “Journal on Mobility Cultures and Policies” <https://rebalancemobility.eu/journal-mobility-cultures-and-policies/>

Observatory: In this page visitors find information about related forums & journals, articles, studies and a video library <https://rebalancemobility.eu/observatory/>

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Insights- In this page visitors have access to experts and thinkers profile and to REBALANCE Talks registration <https://rebalancemobility.eu/insights-on-mobility-cultures-policies/>

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Insights on Mobility Cultures & Policies

Relevant humanists and social scientists are nowadays reflecting on how emerging technologies are changing mobility cultures and social values, and how values affect mobility practices and policies. The Coronavirus pandemic makes the world a living lab to further develop these reflections. Policies restraining or prohibiting individual freedom to move and surveying people's daily lives are applied to protect social health (a prevailing citizen's right). These policies cause huge economic costs on many sectors and companies (e.g. tourism) but also benefits to few others (e.g. telecommunications, e-commerce). Policies restraining physical mobility create social distress and psychological suffering to many; however it is imperative to apply these policies to save millions of lives worldwide. Furthermore, new and more disruptive technologies will create ethical dilemmas in the near future, for example to what extent we humans can rely on intelligent machines to make better decisions for ourselves and others. The language and everyday categories we presently use (e.g. public interest/common good, individual/social, private/public, utility/meaning, behaviour/values, science/art, data/knowledge, cost/benefit, consumer/producer, local/global...) need to be redefined if we want to be able to imagine new and better futures for all. Many people, from artists to scientists and politicians, have already provided inspiring thoughts on these issues.

Coming up

Conversation with Mateu Turró

Mateu Turró is Honorary A. Director of the European Investment Bank (EIB), Doctor Engineer by UPC, Consultant/advisor on transport and urban development, focused on project appraisal, financing and PPPs, Chairman of the Advisory Council of CENIT (Centre for Innovation in Transport).

Date and Time: 18.03.2021 at 16:00h to 17:00h (CET)

Location: Online Event

[Register for the event](#)

Coming up

Conversation with Andreas Knie

Andreas Knie is a political scientist, head of the Research Group Digital Mobility and Social Differentiation at the Science Center Berlin for Social Research, and professor at the Technical University Berlin. Within the fields of research Knie is an expert in science, technology and mobility.

Date and Time: 25.03.2021 at 16:00h to 17:00h (CET)

Location: Online Event

[Register for the event](#)

Coming up

Conversation with Judy Wajzman

Judy Wajzman is the Anthony Giddens Professor of Sociology. She was a Visiting Professor at the Centre for Women in Business at London Business School. She was President of the Society for Social Studies of Science and is currently a Visiting Professor at the Oxford Internet Institute.

Date and Time: 1.04.2021 at 16:00h to 17:00h (CET)

Location: Online Event

[Register for the event](#)

Alain Bonnafous

Andreas Knie

Andreu Ullied

Barbara Adam

Carl Honoré

Cass R. Sunstein

Chris Nash

Christoph Walther

Daniel Sperling

Dominique Méda

Dragos Simandan

Eva Illouz

Jacques Lévy

Judy Wajzman

Luca Bertolini

Mark Coeckelbergh

Massimo Moraglio

Mateu Turró

Mimi Sheller

Noel B. Salazar

Oriol Nevo

Pekka Himanen

Robert Braun

Robert Cervero

Robert Hassan

Saskia Sassen

Sebastien Bourdin

Tim Cresswell

Werner Rothengatter

Yann Diener

[Suggest other relevant thinkers](#) →

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Example of a Thinker profile page: <https://rebalancemobility.eu/judy-wajcman/>

The screenshot shows a profile page for Judy Wajcman on the REBALANCE website. The page layout includes a header with the REBALANCE logo and navigation links (About, Activities, Talks, Journal, Insights, Observatory). The main content area features a profile picture of Judy Wajcman, a bio identifying her as the Anthony Giddens Professor of Sociology at the LSE, and a list of relevant books and papers. A quote from her work is displayed in a light blue box. Below the bio, there are video thumbnails and a 'Learn more' button. At the bottom of the profile section, there is a 'Share This Story, Choose Your Platform!' section with social media icons and a 'Related Posts' section with four small profile pictures.

Social networks / Contact / and Private policy

As it could be seen at the footer of each of the platform webpage, there is the EC logo with legal information about the project, as well as the links to REBALANCE social media channels and the link to the contact page.

2 CONCLUSIONS

REBALANCE New Mobility Cultures and Policies Hub serves as an interactive and knowledge-sharing platform (in English). It is a useful resource for partner organizations, stakeholders, the media, and the public at large. It publicizes the project's aims and objectives, and showcase the results as they become available. It is also used to promote the project's online events and establishes synergies with all the project WPs.

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It also includes as a background reference a virtual library with articles and studies (or links) in mobility cultures and policies identified in WP3, WP4 and WP5, as well as those related to thinkers participating in WP2 activities.

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